

Variational Bayesian Learning of SMOGs: Modelling and Implementation

Evangelos Roussos

Ronin Institute for Independent Scholarship, Montclair, NJ, USA

eroussos@learning-machines.org, evangelos.roussos@ronininstitute.org

Abstract

Variational methods are effective tools for approximate inference in Statistical Machine Learning and Computational Statistics that aim at providing a solution to the problem of inference and learning in intractable exact posterior distributions. In this paper, after introducing the general variational Bayesian learning method, we apply it to the modelling and implementation of *sparse* mixtures of Gaussians (SMOG) models, intended to be used as *adaptive priors* for the efficient representation of sparse signals in applications such as wavelet-type analysis. Wavelet decomposition methods have been very successful in denoising real-world, non-stationary signals that may also contain discontinuities. For this purpose we construct a constrained hierarchical Bayesian model capturing the salient characteristics of such sets of decomposition coefficients. We express our model as a Dirichlet mixture model. We then show how variational ideas can be used to derive efficient methods for bypassing the need for integration in Bayesian inference: the task of integration becomes one of optimisation. We finally apply our SMOG implementation to the problem of denoising of time-series with transient effects.

Keywords: Probabilistic Machine Learning; Signal Processing; Variational Bayesian Learning; Sparse Recovery; Wavelet-Based Models; Denoising; Geodesic Signals; Adjustment of Observations

1 Introduction

Sparse decompositions of signals, images, and data have found widespread use across a wide array of scientific disciplines and practical applications. The key insight is that while modern sensors generate signals containing an often overwhelming amount of data, the useful information in them can often be described by a much smaller number of ‘primitives’. Early work in the compression, representation, and cleaning of seismic and other nature-generated signals, for example, has led to the discovery of wavelets, bases that span signal spaces in a very efficient manner. A central modern motivation for sparsity comes from applications such as compressed sensing and computation (*sparse recovery*).

The idea in *sparse representation* is to describe the original signals using such ‘atomic decompositions’, with the coefficients of the decomposition serving as the resultant ‘code’. This code is almost always sparse for a wide variety of signals, meaning that most coefficients will be almost zero with only a small percentage of them being significantly larger than zero. Statistically, the empirical histograms of those sets of coefficients are highly peaked at zero. Our aim in this paper is to use appropriate probability density functions to describe such distributions. We would also like to incorporate notions of uncertainty in the model parameters. For that purpose we propose to use the *sparse mixture of Gaussians* (SMOG) model as a flexible prior on the decomposition coefficients, learnt under the *Bayesian* framework. Olshausen and Millman [?] have used this prior for learning sparse codes of natural images under a combined Maximum Likelihood/Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) framework. Roussos, Roberts and Daubechies [?] have used a similar model for functional MRI data, employing wavelet decompositions in an independent component analysis setting, but learned under a Variational Bayes framework. A wide range of other applications have used similar models from a maximum likelihood, maximum a-posteriori, and expectation-maximisation perspective. In this paper we give a detailed description of the SMOG method and its implementation and place it in the wider context of computational statistical inference.

Bayesian inference is mainly concerned with posterior inference, using Bayes’ theorem as our vehicle [?]. This formally encodes the update of our prior knowledge in light of new data. We express our prior beliefs regarding the various uncertain quantities of our models in the form of Bayesian *priors*. The data, on the other hand, are probabilistically linked with the parameters of our models using the likelihood. A defining characteristic of the Bayesian approach is, therefore, that model parameters are regarded as random quantities, described by distributions. This distinguishes Bayesian learning from standard frequentist approaches. In the Bayesian approach learning and inference are treated exactly the same.

Posterior elicitation, however, puts on us the burden of computing often intractable, high-dimensional integrals, as we need to *integrate out* certain model parameters and hidden variables, often regarded as ‘nuisance variables’. A number of methods have been developed from the Bayesian community to tackle this problem, ranging from deterministic ones, such as the Laplace approximation, to stochastic, the main representative of which are the various MCMC approaches. While extremely powerful, MCMC methods are also computationally demanding. Another deterministic approach, based on principles of Statistical Physics, which is more flexible than the Laplace approximation while being much more computationally efficient than MCMC, is offered by *variational methods* [?], [?]. These make mean-field approximations to the Bayesian evidence and joint posteriors to derive a rigorous lower-bound to the evidence and a set of ‘self-consistent’ update equations for the unknowns of the problem.

The rest of the paper derives the general variational Bayesian (VB) framework and then applies it to the particular problem of learning the sparse mixture of Gaussians model, with a special emphasis to encoding sets of coefficients from

sparse signal representations of Geodetic and other Earth observation signals.

2 Variational Bayesian Learning of SMOGs

In this section we present a hierarchical Bayesian model for modelling sparse sets of decomposition coefficients in a basis, such as wavelet coefficients. The general problem we aim at solving is the following: given a noisy signal, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and an appropriate basis, $\Phi = \{\varphi_\lambda\}_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$, we first decompose \mathbf{x} in Φ , obtaining the corresponding coefficients, $\mathbf{c} = (c_\lambda)_{\lambda \in \Lambda}$. If the signal is well-representable in the basis, then only a few significant coefficients will be needed in order to describe it, leading to a *sparse* representation. The majority of the coefficients will then be ‘small’ and can be attributed to noise. In statistical terms, the empirical histogram of the c_λ s will be typically *supergaussian*, i.e. heavy tailed and highly-peaked at zero. By separating those two classes of coefficient magnitudes and keeping only the large ones, we effectively perform denoising. The following subsection presents the mathematical model of this process.

2.1 Bayesian Modelling of Sparse Wavelet Coefficients

2.1.1 The Bayesian SMOG model

The model should capture the desired or expected properties of those sets of expansion coefficients in the prior, informed by the observed behaviour of those decompositions in practice. It should also be constrained enough to enforce sparsity while at the same time being flexible enough to capture a wide range of decompositions of a variety of signals.

A flexible prior that is at the same time mathematically tractable is a mixture distribution. For an M -component model, a mixture-of-Gaussians (MOG) can be expressed mathematically as a linear combination of component densities,

$$p(y_n | \theta_{\text{SMoG}}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \pi_m \mathcal{N}\left(y_n; \mu_m, \frac{1}{\beta_m}\right), \quad (1)$$

where (μ_m, β_m) are the mean and precision (inverse variance) parameters of the m -th Gaussian component over y_n and $\{\pi_m\}_{m=1}^M$ are mixing proportions. Since the π_m s are non-negative the MOG is also a *convex* combination of Gaussians. We collect the learnable parameters in a vector $\theta_{\text{SMoG}} = \{\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}\}$. Each component in the mixture may be interpreted as a ‘state’. In our implementation we enforce sparsity by restricting the general mixture of Gaussians model to be a two-component, zero co-mean mixture: one component, with small variance, captures non-active coefficients while the other, with large-variance, capture active ones. Olshausen and Millman also propose a ternary version of the MOG model for sparse coding in [?], in which the data can assume three states: non-active, active negative and active positive; see Fig. 1b. That is, while the ‘off’ mode is the same as before, the ‘on’ mode has two sub-modes. The hope here is that this PDF will better describe the behaviour of coding

Figure 1: Sparse mixture of Gaussians (SMoG) density, here used as an adaptive prior for the decomposition coefficients, $\{c_\lambda\}$, of a sparse signal. Blue/green curves: Gaussian components; thick black curve, mixture density, $p(c_\lambda)$. In multiscale, wavelet-type analysis, a separate SMoG is placed on each dyadic scale.

coefficients, focusing on the meso-scale coefficients. However, Olshausen and Millman reported minimal benefits from this added complexity. Therefore, we will use a two-state model in this paper. In [?] the state variables of the ternary model are inferred using Gibbs sampling while the model parameters are learnt by a gradient, maximum likelihood algorithm. In this paper, we instead employ a fully Bayesian model and learning algorithm to the problem.

In multiscale, wavelet-type analysis, a separate SMoG is placed on each dyadic scale, resulting in a collection of parameters, $\theta_{\text{SMoG}} = \bigcup_j \theta_{\text{SMoG}_j}$, and adapted to the characteristics of the particular signal. We name our model a *sparse MoG* (SMoG). The Bayesian SMoG model probability density is shown in Fig. 1.

Introducing hidden variables. In order to derive a computationally efficient learning algorithm, we first start by performing the following ‘thought experiment’: *if* we had access to the state of each data point, as being active or non-active, the task of learning the parameters of the two components would be much easier, as the two components would then be decoupled and we would only need to learn the parameters of the individual component that the data points would be assumed to have been generated from. We will regard those unknown states as ‘missing’ data and introduce a set of latent *indicator* variables, ξ_n , such that when “filled in” by our algorithm, we will achieve our goal. The component indicators therefore play a very important role in this model. They essentially signify the component, m , at which the data point n becomes (probabilistically) assigned to; that is, in the case of SMoGs for wavelet analysis, *whether a particular wavelet basis φ_λ is significant or not* for a specific dataset. This decision happens at the ‘inference’ stage of the Bayesian algorithm, via

the corresponding posterior distribution, i.e. after the model has seen the data. The latent variables ξ_n effectively work as ‘switches’, turning wavelet bases ‘on’ or ‘off’ for a particular signal. The *likelihood* for the SMOG model after the introduction of the latent variables becomes:

$$p(y_n|\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}}) = \sum_{m=1}^M p(\xi_n = m|\boldsymbol{\pi}) p(y_n|\xi_n, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) . \quad (2)$$

Each component indicator, ξ_n , “picks” one of M components for its corresponding data point y_n with a-priori probability $p(\xi_n = m|\boldsymbol{\pi})$, for all n .

Probability assignments. We will formulate our SMOG model as a Dirichlet mixture model. In Bayesian modelling, the assumed distribution of the latent variables as well as the priors over the parameters of the model must be stated, as they are an integral part of the model itself. The indicator variables of the SMOG components, $\boldsymbol{\xi} = (\xi_n)$, are assigned a categorical (or, generalised Bernoulli) distribution, such that $p(\xi_n = m|\boldsymbol{\pi}) = \pi_m, \forall n$. The above can be thought of as the *soft assignment* $n \mapsto m$, of the n th data point to the m th component, with probability $p(\xi_n = m|\boldsymbol{\pi})$. This prior can be more conveniently written as

$$p(\boldsymbol{\xi}|\boldsymbol{\pi}) \doteq \text{Cat}(\boldsymbol{\pi}) = \prod_{n=1}^N \pi_m^{[\xi_n=m]} , \quad (3)$$

where the symbol $[\cdot]$ is the Iverson bracket, which is equal to 1 if its argument is true and 0 otherwise. This form offers some conceptual advantages with respect to expressing conjugacies in the model and facilitates further mathematical manipulations.

The prior over the model parameters, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}}$, as directly read from the SMOG DAG, is

$$p(\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = p(\boldsymbol{\pi})(p(\boldsymbol{\mu})p(\boldsymbol{\beta})) = p(\boldsymbol{\pi}) \left(\prod_{m=1}^M p(\mu_m) \prod_{m=1}^M p(\beta_m) \right) , \quad (4)$$

with the following assignments:

- The prior over the mixing proportions vector, $\boldsymbol{\pi}$, is a Dirichlet distribution with concentration hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_M)$, with $\alpha_m \geq 0$:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\pi}|\boldsymbol{\alpha}) \doteq \text{Dir}(\boldsymbol{\pi}; \boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{\text{B}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})} \prod_{m=1}^M \pi_m^{\alpha_m-1}, \quad \text{B}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \frac{\prod_{m=1}^M \Gamma(\alpha_m)}{\Gamma(\sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m)} , \quad (5)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ and $\text{B}(\cdot)$ are the Gamma and multivariate Beta functions, respectively. The Dirichlet is sometimes called a ‘distribution over distributions’, since it is a probability distribution on the simplex of sets of non-negative numbers that sum to one [?]. In other words, each draw from a Dirichlet is itself a distribution. It is the conjugate prior of the

Categorical distribution [?]. Note that in the SMOG model, in contrast to the general MoG, it is more logical to assign different hyperparameters α_m for the different components, $m = 1$ and $m = 2$, in the binary case, i.e. have an *asymmetric* prior because, for *sparse* data, we expect that most of the bases should be inactive (‘off’). Therefore, we assign a much larger a-priori concentration parameter, α_1 , corresponding to the peak of the distribution at zero, than α_2 . This means that the a-priori probability of drawing an inactive coefficient c_λ from the model is significantly higher than drawing an active one.

- The prior over each component mean, μ_m , is a Gaussian, with hyperparameters (m_0, τ_0) such that the hyperparameter m_0 of the prior is $m_0 \doteq 0$, implying $\mathbb{E}_p[\mu] = 0$, while we let the algorithm *learn* the posterior hyperparameters of $q(\mu)$. That is, we do *not* fix the means themselves to 0 but only the prior hyperparameters and let the algorithm learn the actual value of the corresponding posterior hyperparameters itself using an empirical Bayes approach. The above expresses our prior belief that the centres of the distribution of the c_λ are drawn from a hyperprior with mean zero and a small width, τ_0 . This reflects the empirical observation that, for sparse signals, it is highly probable that most wavelet coefficients will be zero:

$$p(\mu_m) \doteq \mathcal{N}(\mu_m; m_0, \tau_0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi/\tau_0}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\tau_0(\mu_m - m_0)^2}. \quad (6)$$

- The prior over each component precision, β_{j_m} , of the j th dyadic scale is a Gamma distribution with hyperparameters (b_0, c_0) . While in general we would often express our lack of prior information in the scales of the β parameters by selecting a vague (‘uninformative’) prior [?], in this case we want to express our expectation that, for sparse signals, again, only a few wavelet coefficients will be significantly different from zero. Therefore, we will select the prior hyperparameters (b_0, c_0) such that the non-active coefficients c_λ , which will form the majority of the representation, will be neatly concentrated around 0, i.e. assign a high precision to that state, while the few ‘large’ ones will be drawn from a component with a small precision (high variance), to allow “wobble space”:

$$p(\beta_m) \doteq \text{Ga}(\beta_m; b_0, c_0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)b_0^{c_0}} \beta_m^{c_0-1} e^{-\frac{1}{b_0}\beta_m}, \quad (7)$$

where we have used the *scale-shape* parameterisation of the Gamma distribution.

2.1.2 SMOG Bayesian Network

We will express our hierarchical Bayesian model as a directed acyclic graph that is a particular type of a probabilistic graphical model (PGM) called a

Bayesian network, capturing the probabilistic dependence relations among the random variables in our model. In PGMs a node represents a random variable and an edge a statistical dependence. In a Bayesian network, each node has a set of ‘parent’ and a set of ‘children’ nodes. The *conditional probability* of a variable, v , in the model given other variables is represented by that node given its parents, $\text{pa}(v)$. We next introduce the important concept of a *Markov blanket*: the Markov blanket of a node is the set of its parents, children, and co-parents (i.e. the other parents of its children). A Markov blanket defines a notion of ‘*neighborhood*’ in Bayesian networks: the probability of a random variable is independent of all other variables outside of its Markov blanket. These concepts will prove to be essential during learning and inference because they localise computations. The Bayesian network for the model in Fig. 2.

2.2 Variational Bayesian inference

We now show how variational ideas can be used in order to construct methods for approximating the integrals necessary for Bayesian learning [?], [?]. In variational Bayesian (VB) learning, the objective function to be optimised is the *negative free energy* (NFE) of the system, \mathcal{F} . The NFE forms a *lower bound* to the log-evidence of the model, $\log p(\mathcal{Y})$, and is therefore the Bayesian quantity that we seek to maximise: see Fig. 3.

We will now show how the NFE is derived. Starting from the marginal likelihood, $\mathcal{L} = p(\mathcal{Y})$ and expanding it in terms of the joint distribution over the full generative probabilistic model, represented in the directed graphical model \mathcal{G} , including the unknowns, $\mathcal{U} = \mathcal{X} \cup \Theta$ (comprising the latent variables and the model parameters), and the data, \mathcal{Y} , we find the important relation

$$\underbrace{\log p(\mathcal{Y})}_{\text{log-evidence}} = \underbrace{\mathcal{F}[q(\mathcal{U})]}_{\text{Negative free energy}} + \underbrace{\text{KL}[q(\mathcal{U})||p(\mathcal{U}|\mathcal{Y})]}_{\text{Kullback-Leibler divergence} \geq 0}. \quad (8)$$

The second term in the equation above expresses the “distance”¹ between the variational posterior, $q(\mathcal{U})$, and the true posterior, $p(\mathcal{U}|\mathcal{Y})$, quantified by the Kullback-Leibler divergence, or relative entropy, $\text{KL}[q||p]$. This is a non-negative quantity; therefore the NFE is a rigorous lower bound to the log-evidence. If the variational posterior equals the true posterior, the NFE *is* the log-evidence. Of course, for all but the simplest statistical models certain approximations have to be made in order for inference to be *tractable*. By choosing a set of approximate distributions that facilitates easier computations, usually by choosing convenient functional forms, such as PDFs in the exponential family, or/and breaking some dependencies in the joint model, the KL divergence becomes non-zero and the NFE lowers. Our goal in Bayesian modelling is first to judiciously choose the above aspects of our model and then maximise $\mathcal{F}[q(\mathcal{U})]$,

¹Note that the KL divergence is not symmetric with respect to commuting its arguments: $\text{KL}(p||q) \neq \text{KL}(q||p)$. The particular form used in the VB method is the one that forces the variational posterior to cover the majority of the probability mass under the true posterior and also allows for easier mathematical derivations.

Figure 2: Bayesian network representation, $\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}$, of a sparse mixture of Gaussian (SMoG) density. Brown rectangles represent ‘plates’, iterating over collections of variables. The plate over n represents the collection $\{(y_n, \xi_n)\}$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, of pairs of state and representation coefficient values, for each data point n . The plates over m represent the parameters of the **set** of M Gaussian components, $\Theta_{\text{SMoG}} = \{(\mu_m, \beta_m)\} \cup \{\pi\}$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, stored in a vector θ_{SMoG} . These collectively model the generally *non-Gaussian* density of the coefficients of a signal. Filled nodes, such as y_n , denote instantiated nodes. Rectangle nodes denote hyperparameters of the model. In multiscale, wavelet-type analysis this DAG is replicated for each dyadic scale, j , as well, resulting in a collection of parameters, $\Theta_{\text{SMoG}} = \bigcup_j \Theta_{\text{SMoG}_j}$.

in order to obtain the tightest possible bound, within the chosen set of distributions. Focusing on the NFE, this can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{F}[q(\mathcal{U})] = \underbrace{\langle \log p(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{Y}) \rangle_q}_{\text{Variational Energy, } \mathcal{E}[p(\mathcal{G})]} + \underbrace{\langle -\log q(\mathcal{U}) \rangle_q}_{\text{Shannon entropy, } \mathcal{H}[q(\mathcal{U})]}. \quad (9)$$

The first term in the above equation, the expected log-probability of the model, i.e. the log-joint $\log p(\mathcal{G})$, with respect to the variational posterior, is called the

Figure 3: The negative free energy (NFE), $\mathcal{F}[q]$, forms a lower bound to the Bayesian log-evidence for a data set under the model, $\log p(\mathcal{Y})$. Their difference is the Kullback-Leibler divergence, $\text{KL}[q||p]$, between the variational posterior, $q(\mathcal{U})$, and the true posterior, $p(\mathcal{U}|\mathcal{Y})$. The NFE is the optimisation function of the VB methodology.

variational energy and the second term is the *Shannon entropy* (information entropy) of the variational posterior over the unknowns. Since the nodes \mathcal{Y} are instantiated to the data, and are therefore fixed quantities, the above integration gives us a functional that maps PDFs in the function space of candidate approximate joint distributions, $\mathcal{Q} = \{q(\mathcal{U})\}$, to \mathbb{R}_+ . This functional we be maximised using functional differentiation below. We will find it computationally convenient later to further decompose the NFE into the following formula:

$$\mathcal{F}[q(\mathcal{U})] = \bar{\mathcal{L}}_{\Theta}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) + \mathcal{H}[q(\mathcal{X})] - \text{KL}[q(\Theta)||p(\Theta)], \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{L}}_{\Theta}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \langle \log p(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}|\Theta) \rangle_q$ is the posterior-averaged complete-data log-likelihood. This form will be useful for the evaluation of the NFE itself later.

Under the mean-field *ansatz*,

$$q(\mathcal{U}) \doteq \prod_{\alpha} q_{\alpha}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}), \quad (11)$$

where the posterior is factorised over subsets of the unknowns, $\mathcal{U} \doteq \bigcup_{\alpha} \mathbf{u}_{\alpha}$, it can be shown that our objective function, \mathcal{F} , can be further written as

$$\mathcal{F}[q(\mathcal{U})] = \sum_{\alpha} \text{KL} \left[\exp \left(\langle \log p(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{Y}) \rangle_{q(\mathcal{U} \setminus \{\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}\})} \right) \parallel q_{\alpha}(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}) \right] + c; \quad (12)$$

in other words, the dependence of \mathcal{F} on the individual q_{α} s is only via their corresponding KL divergencies. Taking the functional derivative and equating it to 0, under the constraint that each q_{α} integrates to one (for it to be a proper probability distribution),

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta q(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha})} \left\{ \mathcal{F}[q(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha})] + \lambda_{\alpha} \left(\int q(\mathbf{u}_{\alpha}) d\mathbf{u}_{\alpha} - 1 \right) \right\} \doteq 0, \quad (13)$$

and by the fundamental lemma of calculus of variations [?], we obtain the corresponding Euler-Lagrange equation for the problem [?]. This in our case simplifies by the fact that the functional does not depend on the derivatives q'_{α} .

Moreover, based on the observation above that the NFE is maximised when the KL divergence is zero, and plugging that into the above two equations, we obtain the final general expression for the optimal variational posteriors:

$$q_\alpha^*(\mathbf{u}_\alpha) = \frac{1}{Z_\alpha} \exp \left(\left\langle \log p(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{Y}) \right\rangle_{q(\mathcal{U} \setminus \{\mathbf{u}_\alpha\})} \right); \quad (14)$$

that is, we integrate over all the other variables with respect to their variational posterior. We see that by following the VB approach *we have transformed an inference problem into an optimisation one, which is often easier to solve.*

The above generic equations of VB learning are then *specialised* for the particular model at hand. That is, based on the Markov relations in the Bayesian network, \mathcal{G} , corresponding to our problem, we can immediately write down the terms arising from the logarithm inside the angle brackets of Eq. (14) and the Markov factorisations in \mathcal{G} . Note that these Markovian relations refer to the *prior*, and not to the mean-field variational assumptions regarding the posterior, which enter the picture only via the mean-field averaging, $\langle \cdot \rangle_q$. In terms of implementation, Eq. (14) basically means that in order to compute the update equation for some unknown \mathbf{u} , $q(\mathbf{u})$, we just need to apply the following generic procedure:

1. Take the log-joint probability, $\log p(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{U})$, expand it into the various terms that correspond to the unknowns $\mathbf{u}_\alpha \in \mathcal{U}$, $\alpha = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{U}|$, and, for each α , keep only its ‘relevant’ terms, i.e. the terms that contain expressions containing the variable \mathbf{u}_α . These are none other than the nodes in the *Markov blanket* of the node \mathbf{u}_α .
2. Take the posterior averages, $\langle \cdot \rangle_q$, of the various terms. If the model is constructed such that the node conditional PDFs (i.e. given their parents) are in the conjugate-exponential family of distributions, these averages will be analytically computable.
3. Rearrange and combine the various sub-terms so that we end up with expression patterns that correspond to known distributions, such as those in the exponential family, to finally find the expression of the update equation for each $q_\alpha(\mathbf{u}_\alpha)$.

Note that if the model is constructed such that it belongs to the *conjugate-exponential* family of distributions, then the functional forms of the variational posteriors will be *of the same form* as their corresponding priors. Essentially, computing the posteriors is equivalent to shifting the priors to a position that balances both the requirement of fidelity with respect to reconstructing the data and the constraints imposed by the prior. This will be directly reflected in the form of the update equations. This means that the variational posterior hyperparameters, $\hat{\psi}_\alpha$, will be ‘moves’ in hyperparameter space, during learning, i.e. shifted versions of the corresponding prior hyperparameters, $\psi_{\alpha,0}$, updated according to the observed data:

$$\hat{\psi}_\alpha = \psi_{\alpha,0} \oplus g(\mathbf{y}), \quad (15)$$

where ‘ \oplus ’ is a generalised addition operator, denoting the fusion of information from the prior and likelihood of node α , and $g(\mathbf{y})$ denotes a generic function of the data—these are specialised for each particular model.

2.3 Applying VB Learning to the SMOG Model

Applying the above general methodology and equations to the particular case of Bayesian SMOGs (where the graphical model is shown in Fig. 2), we obtain the concrete expressions for the NFE and the update equations for the nodes of $\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}$ for this model.

In particular, the ensemble of latent variables and parameters of the model is $\mathcal{U} = \{\boldsymbol{\xi}, \boldsymbol{\theta}\}$. Under the mean-field assumption (Beal, [?]), the variational posterior, $q(\mathcal{U})$, factorises over the elements of \mathcal{U} and, therefore, factors in each unknown can be maximised *individually*:

$$q(\mathcal{U}) = q(\boldsymbol{\xi})q(\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (16)$$

Note that, contrary to popular belief, we do *not* need to make a factorisation assumption over $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}\}$, but only over $\{\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}\}$; the factorisation amongst the parameters “falls out” of the Markovian structure of the DAG [?].

Now, the joint probability of $\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}$, by inspecting the dependencies of the graphical model, is:

$$p(\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}) = p(\mathcal{U}_{\text{SMoG}}, \mathcal{Y}_{\text{SMoG}}) = p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\xi}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta})p(\boldsymbol{\xi}|\boldsymbol{\pi})p(\boldsymbol{\pi})p(\boldsymbol{\mu})p(\boldsymbol{\beta}), \quad (17)$$

where the conditional likelihood (the data likelihood conditioned on the latent variables) is

$$p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\xi}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) = \prod_{n=1}^N p(y_n|\xi_n; \mu_m, \beta_m). \quad (18)$$

This product is represented by the plate over $\{n\}$ in the graphical model of Fig. 2.

The NFE for the SMOG model, given the above graph-structured set of RVs and their corresponding joint probability distribution, $p(\mathcal{G})$, now becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F} &= \left(\langle \log p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\xi}; \boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\beta}) \rangle_{q(\boldsymbol{\xi})q(\boldsymbol{\mu})q(\boldsymbol{\beta})} + \langle \log p(\boldsymbol{\xi}|\boldsymbol{\pi}) \rangle_{q(\boldsymbol{\xi})q(\boldsymbol{\pi})} \right) + \\ &\quad \mathcal{H}[q(\boldsymbol{\xi})] - \\ &\quad \left(\text{KL}[q(\boldsymbol{\pi})||p(\boldsymbol{\pi})] + \text{KL}[q(\boldsymbol{\mu})||p(\boldsymbol{\mu})] + \text{KL}[q(\boldsymbol{\beta})||p(\boldsymbol{\beta})] \right). \quad (19) \end{aligned}$$

The first two terms are the average complete-data likelihood, $\overline{\mathcal{L}}_{\Theta}(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})$, defined above, each latent variable provides an entropy term, and each parameter provides a minus KL divergence. The above expression is equivalent to the (negative of) the Helmholtz free energy in Statistical Physics,

$$\mathcal{F} = - \langle \log p(\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{G}}) \rangle + \mathcal{H}[q(\mathcal{U})],$$

where the first term is minus the ‘variational energy’ and the second is the ‘variational entropy’. Note that the above equation (19) is expressed in terms of the form $\langle \log p(\mathbf{v}_\beta | \text{pa}(\mathbf{v}_\beta)) \rangle$ and $\langle \log q(\mathbf{v}_\alpha) \rangle$, where $\beta \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{U} \cup \mathcal{Y}|\}$ and $\alpha \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{U}|\}$. That is, they correspond to internal and leaf nodes of the SMOG DAG, respectively. We will exploit this observation in our implementation later.

2.3.1 Update equations for the unknowns of the model

We now use the generic update equation for the optimal variational posteriors, Eq. (14), derived in the previous section, and specialise it for our model. As an example, the derivation of the update equations for the precisions, β , will be shown here in detail; the remaining equations are derived similarly.

We first rewrite Eq. (14), with $\mathbf{u} \leftarrow \beta$, as² [?].

$$q^*(\beta) \propto \exp \left[\langle \log p(\xi, \mathbf{y} | \beta) \rangle_{q(\xi)} + \log p(\beta) \right], \quad (20)$$

where the first term is the expected ‘complete-data’ likelihood for β , $\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta]$. This is reminiscent of the so-called Q -function of the expectation-maximisation (EM) algorithm, $Q(\theta^k) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbb{E}_{p(\mathcal{X}|\mathcal{Y})} \left[\log p(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y} | \theta^{k-1}) \right]$, $k = 1, \dots$, where the parameter θ at the right-hand-side is instantiated in the value obtained in the previous iteration. In that method, one then takes the gradient with respect to the parameter θ^k and equates it to zero, to obtain the current point estimate of θ [?]. In the variational Bayesian approach, we instead use the full sufficient statistics to obtain posterior distributions. We will say more about the relation between the VB method and EM later.

Now, the complete-data log-likelihood for a single component β_m is

$$\log p(\xi, \mathbf{y} | \beta_m) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^N \log \beta_m - \frac{1}{2} \beta_m \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \mu_m)^2,$$

due to the i.i.d. data. Therefore, averaging the above over the variational posterior, implies that $\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta]$ can be written as

$$\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta] = \sum_{m=1}^M \bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta_m]. \quad (21)$$

Responsibility-weighted statistics. In order to evaluate the $\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta_m]$ ’s, and equivalent quantities for the other variables in the model, we need the following intermediate quantities. We define the *responsibility* of component m with

²Here we just break up the general expression for the variational posteriors, $q^*(\mathbf{u}) \propto \exp \left(\langle \log p(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{Y}) \rangle_{q(\mathcal{U} \setminus \{\mathbf{u}\})} \right)$, into a prior factor for the particular unknown times a likelihood term, which is reminiscent of the Bayes’ rule. This formulation is mainly used here for demonstrating a simple derivation of the formulæ.

respect to data point n as the posterior probability value

$$\hat{\gamma}_{nm} = q(\xi_n = m), \quad \forall n, m, \quad (22)$$

seen as ‘soft’ assignments of data points to components. This will be implemented as conditional probability tables (CPTs). We now define the following responsibility-weighted statistics (resulting from integrating the data statistics over ξ wrt $q(\xi)$ and over μ_m wrt $q(\mu_m)$):

$$\bar{\pi}_m = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\gamma}_{nm} = \frac{\bar{N}_m}{N}, \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{N}_m = \bar{\pi}_m N, \quad (23)$$

where \bar{N}_m can be interpreted as a pseudo-count of the number of data points that can be attributed to the m -th Gaussian kernel, that is $\bar{\pi}_m$ and \bar{N}_m are the proportion and number of samples that are attributed to component m of the data, and

$$\bar{y}_m = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\gamma}_{nm} y_n, \quad (24)$$

$$\tilde{y}_m^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\gamma}_{nm} y_n^2, \quad (25)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \hat{\gamma}_{nm} (y_n - \mu_m)^2, \quad (26)$$

where $\{\bar{y}_m, \tilde{y}_m^2, \tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2\}$ can be interpreted as the contribution of component m to the average, second moment, and centred second moment (variance) of the data, respectively. Note that these three quantities are the only primary data-dependent quantities; all other quantities are derivative ones.

Using the above, we obtain the following expression for the integral $\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta_m]$, as an expression in $(\beta_m, \log \beta_m)$:

$$\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta_m] = \frac{1}{2} \bar{N}_m \log \beta_m - \frac{1}{2} N \tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2 \beta_m. \quad (27)$$

Because both $\bar{\mathcal{L}}[\beta]$ and $p(\beta)$ split into sums over m (Eqns (21) and (4), (7), respectively), the precisions, β , also factorise: $q(\beta) = \prod_{m=1}^M q(\beta_m)$. Combining the exponential term, Eq. (27), with the Gamma log-prior, and collecting the terms in β_m and $\log \beta_m$, we finally have the following variational update equation for the precisions, in log-space:

$$\log q(\beta_m) = \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{N}_m + c_0 - 1 \right) \log \beta_m - \left(\frac{1}{2} N \tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2 + \frac{1}{b_0} \right) \beta_m. \quad (28)$$

We conclude that the optimal form for the $q(\beta_m)$ is a Gamma distribution with hyperparameters, (\hat{b}_m, \hat{c}_m) , given by:

$$\hat{b}_m = \left(\frac{1}{b_0} + \frac{1}{2} N \tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2 \right)^{-1}, \quad (29a)$$

$$\hat{c}_m = c_0 + \frac{1}{2} N \bar{\pi}_m = c_0 + \frac{1}{2} \bar{N}_m. \quad (29b)$$

Note that both hyperparameters are expressed in the form of Eq. (15), as a sum of the corresponding prior hyperparameter plus a data-dependent term. The update equation for the \hat{b}_m variational hyperparameter, in particular, is of the form of a harmonic mean between two precision terms³. This is a typical form for scale variables such as this, i.e. when the sequence to be averaged is comprised of rates.

Terms such as those in Eqns (29a) and (29b) can be thought of as ‘*messages*’, sent from the Markov blanket of the node β_m in the Bayesian network \mathcal{G} to it. We will see later how these quantities can be formally rewritten as terms of a unified, conjugate-exponential family distribution framework. For now, it is interesting to observe, however, that node β_m gets only one message from its parents (the terms $\frac{1}{b_0}$ and c_0) while it gets N messages from its children and co-parents (the terms $\frac{1}{2} \tilde{\sigma}_{y_m}^2$ and $\frac{1}{2} \bar{\pi}_m$). These cardinalities are exactly the cardinalities of those connectivities (edges) in \mathcal{G} .

The remaining update equations are as follows⁴. The hyperparameters, $(\hat{m}_m, \hat{\tau}_m)$, of the variational posterior over the Gaussian kernel means, μ_m , are updated based on equations

$$\hat{\tau}_m = \tau_0 + \bar{\tau}_m, \quad (30)$$

where $\bar{\tau}_m$ is the responsibility-weighted average $\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma_{nm} \langle \beta_m \rangle = \bar{N}_m \langle \beta_m \rangle$, which is the data-dependent ‘message’ coming from the children and co-parents of node μ_m , and

$$\hat{m}_m = \frac{1}{\hat{\tau}_m} (\tau_0 m_0 + \bar{\tau}_m \bar{m}_m); \quad (31)$$

that is, \hat{m}_m is a weighted average of prior and data-dependent quantities, where \bar{m}_m is the responsibility-weighted ratio $\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma_{nm} y_n}{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma_{nm}} = \frac{\bar{y}_m}{\bar{\pi}_m}$.

The mixing hyperparameters, $\{\hat{\alpha}_m\}$, of the variational posterior $q(\boldsymbol{\pi})$ over the mixing parameters, $\boldsymbol{\pi}$, are updated via

$$\hat{\alpha}_m = \alpha_0 + \bar{N}_m. \quad (32)$$

That is, the ‘data counts’ are added to the ‘prior counts’.

³This expression is, up to a proportionality constant, the harmonic mean [?], $x \oplus_h y = \left(\frac{\frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{y}}{2} \right)^{-1}$.

⁴Note that from now on, for convenience, we drop the star notation for the q^* s.

Finally, the posterior of the latent indicator variables, $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, is updated based on the equation

$$\hat{\gamma}_{nm} = \frac{\tilde{\gamma}_{nm}}{\mathcal{Z}_n}, \quad (33)$$

where

$$\tilde{\gamma}_{nm} = \tilde{\pi}_m \left[\left(\tilde{\beta}_m \right)^{1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} \langle \beta_m \rangle \left\langle (y_n - \mu_m)^2 \right\rangle_{q(\mathbf{y}, \boldsymbol{\mu})} \right) \right], \quad (34)$$

and

$$\mathcal{Z}_n = \sum_{m'} \gamma_{nm'}, \quad (35)$$

ensuring that $q(\xi_n)$ is a properly scaled probability density. The above update equation takes $\{(y_n), (y_n^2)\}$, the data sufficient statistics, as input. Note how Eq. (34) reflects Bayes' theorem: the first factor comes from the prior and the expression inside the square brackets comes from the likelihood. For the categorical latent indicators, $\boldsymbol{\xi}_n$, it also holds that $\langle \xi_{nm} \rangle = \gamma_{nm}$. The tilded quantities in the above equations are the *exponential parameters*⁵ [?]

$$\tilde{\pi}_m \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^{\langle \log \pi_m \rangle_q} \quad (36)$$

and

$$\tilde{\beta}_m \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^{\langle \log \beta_m \rangle_q}. \quad (37)$$

These are computed by

$$e^{\langle \log \pi_m \rangle_q} = \exp \left(\Psi(\hat{\alpha}_m) - \Psi(\bar{\alpha}) \right), \quad \text{where } \bar{\alpha} = \sum_{m'} \hat{\alpha}_{m'}, \quad (38)$$

and

$$e^{\langle \log \beta_m \rangle_q} = \hat{b}_{\beta_m} \exp \left(\Psi(\hat{c}_{\beta_m}) \right), \quad (39)$$

respectively, where $\Psi(\cdot)$ is the digamma function, defined as the logarithmic derivative of the Gamma function,

$$\Psi(x) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{d}{dx} \log \Gamma(x) = \frac{\Gamma'(x)}{\Gamma(x)}. \quad (40)$$

Note that although no functional forms for the variational posteriors were assumed, due to conjugacy the deduced posteriors have the same functional form as the priors.

⁵Compare this parameterisation of the exponential family with the *mean parameterization*.

Update schedule. The update equations above form a system of coupled nonlinear equations, which must be solved iteratively. We note in particular that computations in this type of network are *local*, in terms of quantities belonging only in the Markov blanket of each node. Starting from an initial guess for the unknowns, $(\boldsymbol{\xi}^{(0)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(0)})$, the inference algorithm cycles through the update equations (21)–(40), using the moments calculated at each node of the graphical model $\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}$, until convergence. The updates may be performed in a VEM way [?], [?]. However, this is not necessary, since, as stated above, in the Bayesian approach learning and inference are treated exactly the same. Therefore, the general formulation can be used without any distinction into model parameters and latent variables.

2.3.2 Evaluating and interpreting the negative free energy

The negative free energy of the SMOG model,

$$\mathcal{F}[q(\boldsymbol{\xi}), q(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}})] = \bar{\mathcal{L}}_{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \mathbf{y}) + \mathcal{H}[q(\boldsymbol{\xi})] - \text{KL}[q(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}}) \| p(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}})], \quad (41)$$

can now be evaluated using the quantities derived above. It turns out that many of the terms in $\mathcal{F}[q(\boldsymbol{\xi}), q(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{SMoG}})]$, coming from the various nodes in $\mathcal{G}_{\text{SMoG}}$, conveniently cancel out, greatly simplifying the final expression for the free energy. The expression for the NFE of the M -component SMOG is:

$$\mathcal{F}_M = \sum_{m=1}^M \log \left(\frac{\Gamma(\hat{\alpha}_m)}{\Gamma(\alpha_{0,m})} \right) - \log \left(\frac{\Gamma \left(\sum_{m'=1}^M \hat{\alpha}_{m'} \right)}{\Gamma \left(\sum_{m'=1}^M \alpha_{0,m'} \right)} \right) + \quad (42a)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \left[\log \left(\frac{\Gamma(\hat{c}_m)}{\Gamma(c_{0,m})} \right) + \hat{c}_m \log \hat{b}_m - c_{0,m} \log b_{0,m} \right] + \quad (42b)$$

$$- \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\tau_0}{\hat{\tau}_m} - 1 \right) \log \frac{\tau_0}{\hat{\tau}_m} + \tau_0 (\hat{m}_m)^2 \right] + \quad (42c)$$

$$- \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{\gamma}_{nm} \log \hat{\gamma}_{nm} + \quad (42d)$$

$$+ N \left(-\frac{1}{2} \log 2\pi \right). \quad (42e)$$

Note that \mathcal{F}_M is expressed solely in terms of the prior and posterior *hyperparameters*, $\boldsymbol{\psi}_0, \hat{\boldsymbol{\psi}}$, of the model. The first three lines come from the hyperparameters of $\boldsymbol{\pi}, \boldsymbol{\beta}$, and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$, respectively, as a measure of distance between the assumed prior and the inferred variational posterior, expressed in terms of their partition functions (their denominators); the next is an entropic term, measuring how well the model fits the data; and the last term, which is proportional to the cardinality of the dataset, N , effectively lowers the NFE by that amount, and is a reflection of the ‘aleatory’ uncertainty in modelling a wide variety of data by a particular model.

3 Application: Variational Bayesian SMOG for Signal Denoising

The goal here is to reconstruct an unknown function, f , from noisy data. We will use a flexible representation of the signal in a new basis, adapted to the localised features of the data, in a way that only a few basis functions will be needed in order to describe the signal. This is a reflection of the *sparsity* property in that particular basis: most of the coefficients of the representation will be small, and correspond to the noise, and only a few of them will be significant, and correspond to the signal.

We now review some of the basic properties of wavelets that are of importance to our framework next. Wavelets, and other wavelet-like function systems⁶, are a natural way to model *sparsity* and *smoothness* for a very broad class of signals [?]. They form ‘families’ of *localized*, oscillating, bandpass functions that are dilated and shifted versions of a special function called ‘mother wavelet’, ψ . As such, they inherently contain a notion of *scale*, the whole family spanning several scales from coarse to fine. This property allows them to form multi-resolution decompositions of any finite-energy signal, \mathbf{f} .

In the classical setting, wavelets together with a carefully chosen, lowpass function, the ‘scaling function’, ϕ , can form orthonormal bases for $L^2(\mathbb{R})$. Let us denote such a basis with $\mathcal{D} = \{\phi_k\} \cup \left(\bigcup_j \{\psi_{j,k}\}\right)$, where j denotes the scale and k the shift. We can then perform *wavelet expansions* (inverse wavelet transforms) of the form

$$\mathbf{c} \mapsto \mathbf{f} \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{f} = \sum_k c_k^{(\phi)} \phi_k + \sum_j \sum_k c_{j,k}^{(\psi)} \psi_{j,k}, \quad j, k \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (43)$$

where⁷ $\varphi_\lambda \in \left\{ \phi_k(t) \equiv \phi(t - t_k), \psi_{j,k}(t) \equiv 2^{j/2} \psi(2^j t - t_k) \right\}_{j,k}$ is an element in \mathcal{D} , and the scaling and wavelet coefficients, $c_\lambda \in \mathcal{C} = \left\{ c_k^{(\phi)} \right\} \cup \left(\bigcup_j \left\{ c_{j,k}^{(\psi)} \right\} \right)$, known as the ‘smoothness’ (or ‘approximation’) and ‘detail’ coefficients, respectively, are computed by taking inner products—measures of similarity—of the corresponding bases⁸ with the signal:

$$\lambda : \quad c_\lambda \equiv \tilde{\mathbf{f}}_\lambda = \langle \mathbf{f}, \varphi_\lambda \rangle. \quad (44)$$

We will model these wavelet coefficients using the SMOG model.

⁶Such as wavelet packets, local cosine bases, curvelets, ridgelets, and a whole other variety of bases.

⁷To unclutter notation, we will use a single generic index, λ , to index bases and their corresponding coefficients and the symbol φ_λ for the bases, when appropriate, since the elements in \mathcal{D} can be ordered as $\lambda = \lambda(b, j, k) = 1, \dots, \Lambda = |\mathcal{D}|$. The symbol b indexes the ‘subband’, i.e. the subset of wavelets corresponding to a particular direction, in higher dimensional wavelets.

⁸More precisely, the dual (analysis) wavelet, $\tilde{\varphi}_\lambda$, which, in the case of an orthonormal basis, is identical to φ_λ .

3.1 Wavelet Analysis of Geodetic signals

The theoretical developments above will be demonstrated by analyzing simulated Geodetic time-series with transient effects in a noisy setting.

Large-scale Geodetic time-series often contain both periodic and transient effects and are corrupted by coloured noise. We simulated two sinusoids, corresponding to annual and semiannual harmonic functions, plus a transient signal composed of a sigmoidal function, and added white noise as well as coloured noise of comparable amplitude to the signal, using an autoregressive (AR) model, in order to test the ability of the algorithm to detect the signal. We then used a wavelet basis from the ‘Symmlet’ family with filter length 8, and kept the wavelet coefficients using a low-frequency cutoff of $J_0 = 6$. The simulation was then run 100 times. A typical run is shown in Fig. 4. We see that the algorithm has managed to successfully reconstruct the signal, despite the high level of noise. It has also managed to follow the change at $t = 5$, due to the transient. The average correlation coefficient between the original and reconstructed signal was 0.94929. The denoising metrics of the reconstruction were as follows: mean squared error: 0.826791, mean absolute error: 0.741917, signal to noise ratio: 5.153647db, peak signal to noise ratio: 12.123027db, and cross correlation: 0.949288.

4 Conclusions

In this paper the variational Bayesian method was used to learn a constrained version of the general Gaussian mixture model specifically tailored to model sparse sets of decomposition coefficients, such as those obtained from wavelet-type decompositions of signals. Modelling those coefficients under a mean-field approximation allows an efficient algorithm to be derived. The general derivation of the equations of variational inference was shown, connections with relevant Statistical Physics concepts was given, and then the specific update equations and negative free energy functional for the SMOG model were derived in the context of Bayesian networks. Particular emphasis was given to the locality of computations offered by the structuring of sets of random variables in a DAG with probabilistic semantics.

The above experiment was a proof of concept, in order to introduce the Bayesian framework and demonstrate the usefulness of Bayesian statistical analysis in a Geodetic setting. Experimental data with real world Geodetic data will be reported in a forthcoming publication.

A comparison with Markov Chain Monte Carlo using Gibbs sampling (which provides somewhat similar expressions and piecemeal update philosophy but approaching the problem from a stochastic simulation viewpoint), in terms of quality of results and running time with experimental data, is a topic of ongoing research.

Figure 4: Detection of transient signals in noisy Geodetic time series. Blue line: annual and semiannual harmonic signals. Brown line: transient signal. Gray dots: a mixture of white noise as well as coloured noise. Lower panel: green line: original signal, red line: reconstruction by the algorithm.

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